

Abstract

The cause of failure of society to achieve sustainability, solution and proper cure to cancer is presented.

Optimizing life

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1 Intro

While cancerous society may recognize that its life is unsustainable, its solutions will generally be fake and won't lead to sustainability rather maintenance of business as usual, only differently titled.

Most recently, this is a case with *green* production of energy and other products. While renewable energy should be part of sustainable life, it is not a sole requirement for sustainability. And, as others already realized, society may be slowly transitioning to more renewable sources of energy and recycling of products but this is far from sustainable practice[1].

2 Cause

2.1 Of cancer

Polarized individuals are not inherently cancerous. Two polarized individuals of opposite sex living in symmetric symbiosis are not cancerous to each other and, as such, are less likely to be cancerous to environment - if they are not part of hierarchic society.

The hierarchy in society is the source of potential for cancerous behavior. The stronger the hierarchy and the stronger the inequality between individuals in society, the greater is cancerous potential.

If individuals of one species effectively use other individuals of the same species as slaves or resources (even if formally these are not declared as such), it is highly unlikely that individuals of other species won't be treated as slaves and resources. This includes not only horizontally close species, but the host (god) too, whose living tissue is the living environment for all the interacting species.

One should not fall for promises of a better world with renewable energy and less CO₂ in atmosphere. If rich are still getting richer and poor are getting poorer, if wilderness is still decreasing in area and if wild species are still getting extinct - the cancer is still growing strong.

2.2 Of unsustainability

The root cause of unsustainability in cancerous society is operation on short-term benefits, eventually leading to concentration of consumption with effective discouragement and lack of *in situ* production.

While globalization of information is not necessarily bad, globalization of physical products and services in most cases is.

Basic resources for survival (food, water, breathable air) should always be produced *in situ*. Otherwise this leads to unawareness and lack of understanding and appreciation for wild-life and land that is vital for sustainability of life.

Living in a city is not an excuse for import of basic resources - if you can't produce food in a city then you should either find a way to produce your food/water in a place where there's no land and water or abandon city life.

But in polarized society, even awareness of issues is not enough to trigger change, it can only trigger imaginary response - prayers, talks and re-labeling of business practice.

This is because such people simply do not become conscious of the problem until it starts affecting their short-term interests. And this is why every polarized civilization eventually collapses.

Let me quote A. K. MacDougall, who found numerous and striking similarities between humans and cancer in 1996.[2], yet concluded in the end:

"Is the prognosis for the planet as grim as it is for a patient with advanced cancer? Or will infinitely clever but infrequently wise Homo sapiens alter geocidal behaviors in time to avoid global ruin? Even the most pessimistic doomsayers concede that humans have the capacity to arrest Gaia's deteriorating condition. Cancer cells can't think, but humans can. Cancer cells can't know the full extent of the harm they're doing to the organism of which they are a part, whereas humans have the capacity for planetary awareness.

Cancer cells can't consciously modify their behavior to spare their host's life and prolong their own, whereas humans can adjust, adapt, innovate, pull back, change course.

Gaia's future, and humans' with it, depends on their doing so."

Compare that with the situation 25 years later:

"And while it may be difficult to imagine a protein with two dramatically different faces, it may be even more difficult to contemplate cancer cells exhibiting traits, such as cunning and deception. But the research underway at the University of Basel, and collaborating laboratories, has revealed that TGF- β not only is a two-faced protein, it also is one that seems almost Machiavellian in its activities." [3]

So *we*'ve found that cancer is smarter than we thought and that Earth is more of a living being than not[4], but even now, while the world is dying, *we* are still repeating the words of MacDougall - telling us how smart *we* are and how much potential we have. Yes, *we* are aware of the problem (as much as *we* were 25 years ago), but what makes one think that cancer inside of *us* is not aware of it and that it doesn't have the capacity to change?

Yes, *we* say *we* are innovating, adapting and changing course, after all, *we* are labeling our products and practices *green* and sustainable. But, above all, *we* have evolved *cunning* and *deception*. Perhaps *we* have caught up with *our* cancer rather than the other way around?

No, the cancer inside of *us* might not be conscious of it yet, but, apparently, neither are *we*.

And, as long as *we* are not conscious of it, neither the cancer inside of *us* will be. Or the other way around, if that makes *us* feel better.

3 Solution

To ensure sustainability of life, one should maintain life in symbiosis with local wild-life and environment. Production and consumption of resources should be localized to a home of people in symbiosis (ie. family). Exchange of resources and services should be as local as possible, but nothing should be forced.

Everything should be open and transparent, not *open* and *transparent*, and each and every construction should never be done sacrificing quality of other life.

Life operation should not be selfish, or self-centric.

To achieve sustainability of life, it is crucial:

- to be aware of local eco-system capacity, to have sustainability embedded in subconsciousness while doing conscious work,
- act on possible runaway effects, not talk about them when they happen - weakly oscillating economy of growth and recession following natural patterns is not bad, but anything disrupting balance of the eco-system should not be an option,
- to maintain equality - concentration of goods and services and strong hierarchy should not be an option.

Of course, all these principles are natural to neutralum[5] (naturalum?), however, it will be hard to impossible for neutralum to exercise them in polarized society.

Therefor, isolation is recommended. It will enable neutralums to have satisfying and happy life. It may be, however, that neutralums at key positions in polarized society are keeping it from annihilation - consciously or unconsciously. This might seem good for polarized, but this is not good for anyone when the advantages of neutralum are [ab]used to sustain cancer growth instead of achieving promised sustainability.

Overwhelming evidence strongly suggest this is the case. My recommendation, therefor, is to abandon slavery to polarized and strongly isolate, leave them do what they actually want - annihilate. This will restore balance and enable sustainability of life on the planet, as they will, with annihilation, increasingly be reincarnating into other animals - enabling them to learn to appreciate nature.

Of course, there is a possibility they won't annihilate - perhaps they will evolve consciousness with no annihilation and experience of wild life, however, experience tells me that, generally, this is highly unlikely. Probability for that is equal to a probability of random mutation that will trigger transformation. Such transformation happened to me around the age of 35, however it was not random - I was predetermined to be transformed due to my entanglement with, and past experience of, wild and more evolved life.

Even before the transformation, when I was expressing polarized behavior, I did not have cancerous tendencies and I was avoiding supporting the government and the church because I felt it wasn't right. I was suffering when I was forced to be cancerous and was destined to break free.

Note to neutralum - the devil is very deceiving, a lot of polarized people claim they do not support government, industry, church or whatever - but every single one of them is paying taxes, registering their cars, paying insurances (ie. borrowing and giving money to government through their pension insurance), buying modern products, giving money to church at weddings, funerals, masses... They are all lying and deceiving, both us and themselves. But if you are a neutralum you will eventually realize that these people do not want to change this, effectively, they believe that the system and their consciousness will change spontaneously (magically) if needed and when needed, and that radical, extreme changes to the system and their lifestyle are unnecessary as much as they are undesirable.

Arguments don't work when people operate by feeling, thus, even though these can't argue with logic (truth), they tend to get insulted and become angry - something is deeply embedded into their consciousness telling them that what they do is right. Even if they do admit what they do is wrong and verbally express the desire to change, nothing will be fundamentally changing until their security (zone of comfort) is shattered. Afterwards, they will be faking change (even though they might be convinced they have changed or are changing), but this will be temporary and superficial unless (or until) something deeply embedded into their consciousness doesn't fundamentally change. That something is the soul and required change is the event of transformation that must be triggered (synchronized) with death of a certain individual (not necessary of the same species).

If you are *destined* for this transformation, your faking will be a precursor to this event and you will soon start changing for real. But if you have, as polarized, had cancerous tendencies, then it is highly unlikely that you will fundamentally change in current incarnation - you may be faking neutrality, but you will likely remain polarized.

References

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